

Symmetric model of prime number placement by dual cord at the half-line of the Inverse Fixed cone at 1:3 Pythagoras-1 Vedic Zero, in a fixed numbers matrix:

AUTHORS:

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Principal and main author, researcher and publisher.

(He is MD physician/surgeondiscoverer of the inverse-1 and inverse 19 since 2009, with a dozen progressive publications on-1 inverse, including on Vedic zero , number 19 and -1 inverse .He is the head researcher at Hope research , Athens , Wisconsin ,USA).

2. Theo denOtter.

(He has developed the world's first mathematical method for Placing all numbers and Prime numbers at -1, half-line +3. He is a Professor at Hope research, Athens Wisconsin USA.)

Contributing researchers

1. CenapOzel.

(He has a PhD in mathematics from Glasgow U.K and has strongly assented and acknowledged the inverse -1 by algebra-1 cone since 2016. Currently a Professor of Mathematics at King Abdul Aziz University, Saudi Arabia)

2. Manoj Kumar Srivastav.

(He has a MSc, Pure mathematics(Hope research credentialed as Professor) . He assented on the mathematics , and helped develop the quadratic algebra described here. He is a Mathematics school teacher at Hoogly, West Bengal , India.

3. Mirzahmet Syzdykov,

(MSc(computer science) . He has been asked to develop a computer program based on the manual program of prime number placement developed at Hope research, he has worked on the program but not been able to do this novel program yet. He is at Almaty, Kazakhstan).

Key Words: -1Vedic zero, inverse cone at -1,-1correct zero of Non-linear mathematics, natural decimalization, oscillation of prime numbers at half-line, The 6 constant of mathematics.

Authors signature equation: This mathematics is not of the lineage of current mathematics and to understand and follow this precise mathematics, the reader must understand this precise equation that was not solved by any mathematician or journal in the world prior to this submission

$$(X-Y)=1/(X+Y)$$

$$(X+Y)=1/(X-Y)$$

$$(2Y*X)=(X*Y)*3$$

General solution for the equation $Y=\sqrt{(X^2-+1)}$

Abstract: That numbers expand in a mathematical cone in tandem with the expansion of nonlinear space by geometry , the decimal system placement and Prime number placement are all the natural consequence of a precise inverse cone at 1:3 Pythagoras with mathematical zero, Vedic Zero, that is -1 both by numbers and geometry . Its basic mathematical conclusion is that for the expansion (Cone progression)of space and numbers that are naturally placed at a half line , the zero has to be -1. Period, Please! this logic is fundamental and cannot be discussed further. All numbers oscillate including prime numbers by their unique mathematics.

Toput the proverbial cart before the horse, this mathematics needs no proofs as the proofs are in the matrix of the presentation which should be evident even to nominal mathematical minds . The proof of the oscillation of the prime numbers at the half line is proved by a pure mathematics placement sieve that has been worked till 50 thousand Prime numbers and yet to be programmed as two distinct placement values of prime numbers that are symmetric with two cords of prime numbers (*Mathematically it is impossible to have oscillation of prime numbers, without two defined cords, a single cord cannot oscillate , and there has to be a mathematically well defined half-line*).The proof of the two cords presented in this paper is clear by several methods including a new quadratic algebra which is foreign to current mathematics. The symmetry between these two placements of prime numbers by two cords and oscillations at the half line are synergistically symmetric and as such symmetry across a half line is absolute proof in mathematics.

The authors have shown a single mode of symmetry by the sieve and placement of prime numbers by dual cords, in a placement order of numbers at an inverse cone at -1. Mathematics is the mother of science, and before there was matter there was space , that space is mathematically rational and this rationality is described here in the form of a fixed inverse cone at -1 that allows for the finite spherical expansion of the cone. Mathematically the zero has to be -1 and not null zero for any space to be expansible, and it is obvious the universe of mathematics is expansible and curved .It is shown that prime numbers have a symmetrical placement in the expansion of numbers placement at a half line , as these numbers do indeed hug the half line as clearly shown by the precise mode. The mathematical fact of oscillation of the two cords of prime numbers, in a spiral configuration is suggested in this mathematical analysis. It is clearly shown that prime number 5 is the base configuration and the rest of the numbers continuum follows this configuration, as there is clear evidence that Prime numbers are placed at the half line of an inverse cone 1:3 , and that half line is constant at value 3 and multiples of 3 at the configuration of prime number 5 which has been explained . Also explained is the tight fit of the inverse cone and the mathematical fact that the inverse cone in its expression represents a perfect sphere, with periodic expression of the $3+ \pi$ digits derived at the slope of the Pythagoras 1:3 (value $\sqrt{10}$).

Lastly the base prime numbers shape and control all the manifestations of space and speed, and energy as expressed by their inverse curves. That aspect is far too complex for current mathematics and is not discussed in this paper.

The paper is presented in the following format ‘

Section 1:

Section 11

Section 1 deals with the discovery of the fundamentals of -1 Vedic zero and the pure mathematical placement of numbers at -1 inverse cone which was discovered in 2009 by the author. It also validates the numbers decimal system as being a natural created mathematics at -1 frame first understood by the Vedic people. The main author has published papers on 19 and Vedic zero, referenced below.

Section 11 matches and compliments section 1 by geometric placement and the oscillation of prime numbers by cords of placement. It shows the symmetric synthesis of the oscillation of prime number. This section also defines the bound space unit.

- A. Opening statement to science
- B. Genesis, discovery and the mathematics of Pythagoras 1:3
- C. Mathematical basis of Pythagoras 1:3 and dual Prime number spiral cords cone.
- D. Specific Calculus's of placement and Prediction

Section 1

Subtitle: The Fundamental discovery of -1 inverse and placement of Prime numbers at the half line at the Vedic -1 zero configuration and the natural decimalization of numbers.

(Finite Sphere collapses into a -1 cone and -1 cone expands to a sphere as per the -1 mathematics). This mathematics will be published in the future, in relation to the mathematics of black holes, but basically, $120/(19/3)=360/19$

$120*3=360c$, is mathematically a curved value, and $90*4=360nc$ is non curved squared value, a difficult concept but the reference in the mathematical analysis of $\sqrt{360}$ at the -1 cone as shown, is a curved value as derived at the cone.

The placement of the prime numbers and their geometric oscillation of prime numbers is confirmed by geometry and also by the pure mathematics placement of numbers in precise setting at -1. The oscillation itself at the half line is a symmetry between the alternate prime numbers cords and the cords by the segregation of prime numbers by residual when divided by the value 6. Section 1 deals with the fundamentals of -1 Vedic zero and the pure mathematical placement of prime numbers method shown, as the number settings are by 5 number cords (span) and the half line is +3 (-1, 3, 6, 9, 12...)

The author has already demonstrated by a manuscript that the numbers expansion and precise placement of prime number by formula around a linear half-line at +3, is the precise basis for the inverse expansion of space matrix by natural numbers. The algebraic configuration of the -1 cone at the value (1:X Pythagoras) based on -1 Vedic zero. At the space Y is the slope, 1 upright, base is X, and a half-line at +n is created by full cone (2Y). Numbers expansion is rational and a tight fit at Pythagoras 1:3 cone

$$(X-Y)=1/(X+Y)$$

$$(X+Y)=1/(X-Y)$$

$$(2Y*X)=(X*Y)*3$$

$$\text{At } X=3 \text{ (base) , } Y=\sqrt{3^2+1} \text{ or } \sqrt{10}$$

$$(3-\sqrt{10})=1/(3+\sqrt{10})=0.16227766017$$

$$(3+\sqrt{10})=1/(3-\sqrt{10})=6.16227766017$$

$$6.16227766017-0.16227766017= \textbf{precise 6}$$
, also see diagram, 1,2

The Fixed value 6: This 6 represents the differential in geometry at the cone between the cone progression in two planes, this is a basic geometrical constant as is shown in the diagram. The three constant sides of an equilateral triangle to match at 60 degrees and the offset left is 15 degrees as shown. NOW to inverse the sides to curvature, the only way to do that is with a 1:6 curve (the height of the curve being 1 and the linear span being 6). This is a mathematical constant for the placement of prime numbers by value 6 and 5, and mathematically -1 is expressed at this value

$$15 \cdot 6 = 90$$

$$15 \cdot 4 = 60$$

$$15 \cdot 3 = 45$$

$$(2 \cdot \sqrt{10}) \cdot 3 = (3 \cdot \sqrt{10}) \cdot 2 = \sqrt{(19^2 - 1)} = 6 \cdot \sqrt{10} \text{ or } \sqrt{360}$$

$$\text{AT } X=19(\text{base}), (\text{hypotenuse}) Y = \sqrt{(19^2 - 1)} \text{ or } \sqrt{360}$$

$$19 - \sqrt{360} = 1 / (19 + \sqrt{360})$$

$$19 + \sqrt{360} = 1 / (19 - \sqrt{360})$$

$$(2 \cdot \sqrt{360}) \cdot 3 = (3 \cdot \sqrt{360}) \cdot 2 = \sqrt{(360^2 / 10)} = 6^2 \cdot \sqrt{10}$$

The value 10 (*, +, -) is a natural value in number expansion as is seen in the basic premise of the -1 Vedic zero as well as the numbers setting for prime number placement sieve in the separate file, it oscillates predictably in the 5 span setting as shown below. Value 6 is the constant and one can see the differential between 3 and 19 base in the spatial expansion value to be X6 precise

but mathematical logic is clear that for expansion of this space and placement of prime numbers oscillating symmetrically at the half line (+3) the point of the least has to be at -1. X is base and Y is the hypotenuse.

Thus the span by numbers $(X=3)$, $-1 = (X^2 - Y^2)$ to $19 = (X^2 + Y^2)$ at value 3 as the base, 1 as the perpendicular and $\sqrt{10}$ as the hypotenuse and the value +6 as the modulator. The half line of the cone is +3. All numbers expansion is within the confines of this inverse cone space (Sphere) and is modulated by the half line and oscillation of the non-divisible prime numbers at the half line which is linear. The expression of the inverse cone is curved and the cone in its finite expression is a perfect sphere as is shown in the paper $\sqrt{(360)^2}$. The value +6 as shown above is the constraint. The basis of the Vedic decimal system is the slope $Y^2 (\sqrt{10}^2)$. The correct angle as proved in the paper is $360 / (X^2 + Y^2)$ or $360 / (9 + 10)$, $360 / 19$ degree, each one degree being $6/360 (1/60)$, $360 \cdot 1/60 = 6$

$$6 \cdot \sqrt{10} = \text{sqrt}(360)$$

$$6 \cdot 60 = 360 \quad (360 \cdot 1/60 = 6)$$

Anecdotally the Pi value by ratio is expressed by $(360 - (6 - 1)) / (360 / 3 - (6 + 1)) = 3.141292035$, this is referenced by a published paper. Plus the oscillation of the prime number 6, i.e. -1+1 is prime 5 and prime 7, the only time in the entire number system that +1-1 leads to prime numbers 6, 18, 30, 42, 60, 72, 102,

THE PRIME NUMBER SIEVE AND PLACEMENT AT THE HALF LINE BY VALUE 6 JPRM

HOPE RESEARCHPRIME NUMBER PLACEMENT SEIVE

This is precise mathematics is as shown below developed by Professor Theo denOtter just after inverse 19 was discovered in 2009 in the frame of -1 cone at value 6 and it was subsequently published in one of the papers of Vinoo Cameron , unnoticed till now. the mathematics of placement matches and compliments the geometry of placement in section 11 with a precise half line of +3 in a -1 cone expansion of all numbers including decimal 10 multiples that are arranged in a set zig zag. The following is the method based on 5 cords with a half-line +3, in professor den Otters words. **Please this is verycomplex**, and this is a continuous mathematical placement for all prime numbers starting from the base, and basically demonstrates how non- prime numbers are eliminated. The fundamental use of value 5 and 6 value by arithmetic for the program is the same for all prime number progressions and placement by 5 and 6 values is constant for prime number placement . Please refer to other diagrams as to why -1 manifests itself at value 5 and 6 both by arithmetic and by geometry (take a span of 6 and 1 upright at value 3, the curve that connect 0,1 ,upright, and 6, has a radius of 5 precise, -1 of the span of 6). This program begs a computer program which has been very difficult and has been done manually till about 50 thousand prime numbers. The following is the very basic explanation

Known fact:

Prime numbers are one plus or one minus a divisible number, but when studied further they are all placed **before** or **after** a whole number that is divisible by the **number 6**.

In the case of the numbers one less than the whole number, it always has a residue of 5/6 whereas the number greater than the whole number it is always 1/6 greater than the whole number.

Therefore:

Two distinct sets of prime numbers

Example: **negative prime numbers**

$$5 / 6 = .83333 \text{ or } 5/6$$

$$11 / 6 = 1.83333 \text{ or } 1 \text{ plus } 5/6$$

Positive prime numbers

$$7 / 6 = 1.16666 \text{ or } 1 \text{ plus } 1/6$$

$$13 / 6 = 2.16666 \text{ or } 2 \text{ plus } 1/6$$

Therefore the setting as follows allows us a method of calculating if they are a prime or not.

From the outer edges of the tangent setting a multiple of 5 and 6 is used to delineate + and – prime numbers based on residual 1/6(+) and residual 5/6(-) when divided by the constant 6. These are relevant to the setting of these numbers across the half-line at +3

$$\begin{array}{cc} & -1 \\ 1 & 5 \end{array}$$

7	11
13	17
19	23
25	29

Note: $5 * 6 = 30 + 1 * 5 = 35$

Note:

$5 * 6 = 30 + 35 = 65$ so the next multiple of the prime number 5 will be the number 65.

Also, $7 * 6 = 42 + 35 = 77$ so the next multiple of the prime number 7 will be the number 77

37	41
43	47
$7+42 = 49$	53

Note:

$7 * 6 = 42 + 49 = 91 / 7 = 13$

$13 * 6 = 78, 91 - 78 = 13$

Also $91 + 78 = 169$

Note:

$55 - 30 = 25$ but also $55 - 66 = -11$ which is the prime number on the -1 column

$55 + 30 = 85$ and $55 + 66 = 121$ multiples of 5 and 11

As the program runs all numbers that are left are prime numbers and when multiplied by 6 the rhythm of that number will then move forward to eliminate any multiples of itself.

When given a large number it can be divided by 6 and is absent the residue of $5/6$ or $1/6$ it will never be a prime number.

Setting of numbers:

NOTE!!! This following setting of numbers is in rational 5 cords of numbers(as is prime number placement in cords, described in section 2) ,with +3 half line as constant, this half line is the same as at the inverse cone ,+3 with slope of $\sqrt{10}$ on two frames, half the numbers on one side(2rows) and the other half on the other side (2 rows) . Prime numbers are also in rows that have been shown in section 11 that is what causes the mathematical oscillation at the half line. This pure mathematical method based on

the value 6 and 5 is flawless and 50 ,000 numbers have been done manually, prime numbers are confirmed by this placement the section 1 diagram of the geometry explains the method of oscillation in spatial terms.

37 38 39 40 41

42

43 44 45 46 47

48

(7*6=42+1*7=49)

49 50 51 52 53

(49+42=91)

54

(25+5*6=55)

55 56 57 58 59

(55+5*6=85)

60

(35+5*6=65 +5*6=95)

61 62 63 64 65

(13*5=65+13*6=143)

66

67 68 69 70 71

72

(35+7*6=77+7*6=119)

73 74 75 76 **77**

78

79 80 81 82 83

84

(55+5*6=85+5*6=115)

85 86 87 88 89

90

(49+7*6=91+7*6=133)

(35+5*6=65 +5*6=95+5*6=125)

91 92 93 94 **95**

(13*6=78+13=91+13*6=169)

96

97 98 99 100 101

102

103 104 105 106 107

108

109 110 111 112 113

114

(85+5*6=115+5*6=145) (77+7*6=119+7*6=161)

115 116 117 118 **119**

120

(95+5*6=125+5*6=155)

121 122 123 124 **125**

126

127 128 129 130 131

132

(91+7*6=133+7*6=175)

133 134 135 136 137

138

(65+13*6=143+13*6=221)

139 140 141 142 **143**

144

(85+5*6=115+5*6=145)

(145+5*6=175)

145 146 147 148 149

150

(125+5*6=155 +5*6=185)

151 152 153 154 **155**

156

(119+7*6=161)

157 158 159 160 **161**

162

163 164 165 166 167

168

(91+13*6=169)

169 170 171 172 173

174

(145+5*6=175)

175 176 177 178 179

(133+7*6=175)

180
181 182 183 184 185
186
187 188 189 190 191
192
193 194 195 196 197
198
199 200 201 202 203
204
205 206 207 208 209
210
211 212 213 214 215
216

(143+13*6=221+13*6=299)

217 218 219 220 **221**
222
223 224 225 226 227
228
229 230 231 232 233
234

I have shown only the 5, 7, and 13 prime numbers here so as to keep this less cluttered. Products of each prime numbers is continues and yields prime numbers

The basic prime numbers are already known but by an advancement of 6 gaps on each side the next possible prime is automatically put in place.

Written by Theo den Otter / Hope Research as introduction

So now what are the fixed relationships at the inverse cone 1:3 has with sqrt (360) and -1?, The general equations for the Pythagoras at 1 upright is true for all values of N ,but only at base X=3 2Y *X=sqrt(360)-- Y is the hypotenuse and the full cone is 2Y with a single half line X=3, so a cone at 3

Pythagoras is specific to $\sqrt{(360)}$, . This is a non- linear inordinate oscillation of numbers at the half line as related to expansion of space at the cone

Now for 2Y*X at Pythaogoras-1,reference to the signature equation

X=1 the value is $\sqrt{(8)}$

X=2 the value is $\sqrt{(80)}$

X=3 the value is $\sqrt{(360)}$

X=4 the value is $\sqrt{(1088)}$

X=5 the value is $\sqrt{(2600)}$

X=6thevalue is $\sqrt{(5328)}$

X=7,the value is $\sqrt{(9800)}$

X=8, the value is $\sqrt{(16,640)}$

X=9, the value is $\sqrt{(25,568)}$

X=10,the value is $\sqrt{(40,400)}$

X=19 the value is $\sqrt{(522,728)}$

You add +1 to $(\sqrt{8}+1)$ at value**1=3**

You add +1 to $\sqrt{80}+1$ at value@**2=9** ,

You add +1 to $\sqrt{360}+1$ at value@**3=19**

The value 3 is the end value at the base(1,2,3).Note that this as above manifest only at values at 12,3, value 3 is the end configuration and 19 is the maximum.

This leads to following fixed basis of the Vedic Zero at the cone

$$3^2 + (3^2+1)=19$$

$$3^2-(3^2+1)=-1$$

19 is fundamental to Pythagoras 1:3 as shown above and the following are a parody equations for current mathematics,

$$\sqrt{10} * \sqrt{9} = \frac{\sqrt{360}}{2}$$

$$10 * 9 = \frac{360}{4}$$

Conclusion section 1:The $\sqrt{(360)}$ in the context of -1 cone is a curved value and 3 is an end value, and value 10 is also an end value. 6 is the end value in the transverse frame versus the vertical frame of the cone progression($6*\sqrt{10}=\sqrt{360}$)

$$10 + 9 = \sqrt{(360 + 1)}$$

$$10^2 + 9^2 = \left(\frac{360}{2}\right) + 1$$

$$X^2 - Y^2 = -1 \text{ at the } 1:3 \text{ cone}$$

$$X^2 + Y^2 = 19 \text{ at the } 1:3 \text{ cone}$$

Note that the referenced paper on the value 19 and Vedic zero which is fundamental to 1:3 Pythagoras which is also the basis of decimalization of numbers

The Vedic Zero is the correct zero for non- linear space and the Cone at 1:3 is the least and most finite space which cannot be destroyed. The sphere collapses to -1, not null zero (see JPRM inset file no2) ,it documents what was said in the early stages of this discovery.

Basically it is proven that dynamic expansion of bound space from the least particle , to the maximal finite is modulated with an inverse cone at -1 Vedic zero ; that cone has the same precise configuration in its least as well as its maximum finite. There is no such thing as null zero.

Section11:

1. Opening statement to science
- 2.Genesis, discovery and the mathematics of Pythagoras 1:3
- 3.Mathematical basis of Pythagoras 1:3 and dual Prime number spiral cords.
4. Specific Calculus's of placement and Prediction
- 5.Diagrams of the cone
6. Specific geometry of Pythagoras 1:3, with the spiral prime number fixed placement of the Spiral cords at the cone
- 7.Discussions of the proofs on the cone matrix , including P=NP

Basic mathematical proofs: These are limited as in the text itself, for lack of space

1. Quadratic algebra examples for predicting the next prime number of each cord
2. The precise calculus of the slope of Pythagoras 1:3,with each number cord
3. Diagrammatic proof
4. Various other proofs as in the text

1.Opening statement of understanding to current science:

Mathematics has a genesis and for reasons of logic that rational genesis must have a rational mathematical explanation. By Logic it is, and should have been clear to mathematicians in history that the null zero at a center of a finite space, cannot ever be responsible for the mathematical expansion of that space by

numbers. That zero at the center(*the inverse cone expresses as a perfect sphere, since by geometry and mathematics of the cone $\sqrt{360}$ value is a curved value at the cone. Asphere inverses into a -1 cone which is finite, the mathematical explanation for this fact is extensive and abstract, beyond the scope of this paper but the reader should reference the inset bronze plate file 2 , has to be -1 zero, which is the tangent between the infinite composite and the finite composite.*

2.The genesis of -1 zero:

(See diagram file 3,4) Composite 4 infinite in its inverse can be logically represented by

The displacement of the of the one composite (red above) at 90 degrees (square of $-1*4$ is at 90 degrees precise, and $90 *4$ is 360), that deletion of the one composite at 90 degrees creates Pythagoras 1:3 minus 1 of the composites and this is represented below

The minus one Vedic zero is mathematically best described in its inverse form as

$$3^2-(3^2+1)=-1$$

$$3^2+(3^2+1)=19$$

Since 360 is $90 *4$, the 19 arc on the 1 is functionally curved as is $\sqrt{360}$ and has to be represented by the angle $360/19$ which is further discussed under discussion/ proofs as the proof of this angle negates current approximate trigonometry, but most clearly we have shown that the Pythagoras angles formed at the cone, at the configuration of prime number 5 ($3+2$) have a very definite conformity of the slopes and the angles, which is the basis of all conformity of the numbers at the inverse cone, and this fact is noted here under

P stands for Pythagoras 1:3

$$\frac{\text{slope at}(P 1:3)\sqrt{10}}{\text{slope at}(P1:2)\sqrt{5}} = \sqrt{2}$$

$$\frac{[\textit{Subtended angle at (P 1: 2)}]}{[\textit{subtended angle 1: 3}]} = \sqrt{2}$$

$$\frac{26.79562539225392240^\circ}{\frac{360}{19}^\circ} = \sqrt{2} \text{ precise}$$

Inverse angle(360/19) at the inverse 1:3 cone angle is as shown, inverse of a “perfect sphere”, centered at a -1 point, the -1center zero is essential for the expansion of the cone by prime numbers (the cone configuration, a dual expression of 1:3 Inverse.(-1 Zero here), as shown in the text is an abstract representation of the -1composite in the formation of the angular space of Pythagoras 1:3. The perfect sphere mathematics is abstract and functional mathematic and is partly shown below

$$(\sqrt{360})-19 = 1/(19+\sqrt{360})$$

$$90/(360/19)=4.75 ; 4.75*4=19$$

$$19-360/19=1/19$$

That is why current mathematics is in error, the angle at 1:3 Pythagoras is correct 360/19,current trigonometry is wrong on this, as this is expounded in the proof section, which may be included , Considering that current mathematics has never offered a proof of the precision of their trigonometry

The mathematical concepts of -1 at the inverse cone (See also section 1)

The precise angles in the correct new trigonometry used in our paper as the basis for placement of prime numbers has never before used in history. It clearly proves basic current trigonometry to be flawed and the proof of this angle is presented in the text.

At the configuration of Prime number 5 at the base at the so-called angle of genesis (360/19 at 1:3 Pythagoras and the angle at Pythagoras 1:2 as the tangent. Proofs of these standard degree angles are in the text)

0.....3.....5 (1 is upright value at position 3, see diagram)

$$\sqrt{10}/\sqrt{5} = \sqrt{2}$$

In degrees proportion at the configuration of prime number 5 at the base of the inverse cone

$$\frac{(26.79562539225392240)}{\left(\frac{360}{19}\right)} = \sqrt{2}$$

$$\frac{\left(\frac{360}{19}\right)}{26.79562539225392240} = \sqrt{0.5}$$

This Understanding is backed up by a quadratic algebra that predicts the precise numbers of two separate prime number cords. This is further supplemented by a placement sieve at number 6 done manually by co- author Denotter till 50 thousand prime number placements and sieve, which segregates the prime number placement at the half line at +3(see diagram), into two natural sieved cords , one with residua $n/6= r1/6$ which hugs the half-line tightly , and the other sieved cord of prime numbers $n/6=r5/6$.These two cords , in synthesis with the two separate cords , leads to the spiral oscillation of the prime numbers with flips of polarity at periodic value X6 , as clearly shown in the text , which is confirmed by the two simple sieves that we have of prime numbers (currently manual , with a novel computer program that will place prime numbers in two columns ($1/6, 5/6$ residua) which will confirm the output of prime numbers in polynomial time.

The basic equations of Pythagoras 1:3, sans the equations of the spirals(see also equations in section1)

$$\frac{4}{\left[\left(1 * \frac{1}{0.9}\right) - \left(1 * \frac{0.9}{1}\right)\right]} = \frac{360}{19}$$

$$\left(\frac{360}{19} * \frac{10}{9}\right) - \left(\frac{360}{19} * \frac{9}{10}\right) = 4$$

$$\left[\sqrt{(10)} * \sqrt{(9)} \right] = \frac{\sqrt{(360)}}{2} \text{ for all values of } n$$

2.B: The calculus of the spirals in the frame of Pythagoras 1:3. This is discussed later in the text.

1.Time line of theGenesis and Mathematics of Pythagoras 1:3.by history(very brief)

The inverse 19 was first published by Vinoo Cameron in 2006 just after my very sick son was saved by the grace of Jesus Christ with a 12 hour surgery and also shared in math forum , with 5000 responses and a monument was made in 2009 here at Athens ,Wisconsin referencing to the inverse 19 by the direct hand and grace of my lord. An Amish carpenter had inscribed a 19degree ledge rather than at a 22.5 degree ledge on a window frame because it was more beautiful. The author took note of that and developed the correct concept which is published. It was then Professor Theo Denotter was exposed to the concept and asked to place prime numbers by oscillation at the half line , within a year he did it and it was inserted into a published paper but no one could really understand the papers at that time because of the complexity

It took the author(V.C) ten years and several related published papers to fully resolve the Prime number placement, till the matter was researched at research gate. Professor CenapOzel joined the project a year ago at his request at research gate because he assented to the inverse -1 and he assented to the mathematics and assented to the inverse cone and contributed by his assent and encouragement. I (V.C) then discovered the quadratic cage to solve these two cords partially ,and Ozel assented to the fact of an inverse cone that represented the Pythagoras 1:3. A short paper was published in our name and two others, at research gate on the discovery of the quadratic cage by author Cameron and Ozel. This is referenced in detail in the various references presented below. The research was then fully concluded by Ozel and Cameron at research gate cite on the project “ Spiral cone of Prime numbers” in November and December 2016, and well documented with 70 updates by the author (V.C), documenting the final placement of Spirals and Prime numbers.Thus was inspired the final calculus and all the prime numbers have been unraveled by Quadratic Algebra. A month ago before this publication, Vinoo Cameron discovered the signature equation that no one could solve and posted it with the world widejournals’. JPRM humbly asked for the solution, other elite journals and their editors did not have a clue to solve the equation but lacked the humility to ask for the solution. Several national academies of science could not solve the equation because it did not have the Null zero as basis

Basic placement of prime numbers, cord A, B, 2 of 4 cords:

1,3,5,11,13,17,19,23,29,31,37,41,43,47,53,59,61 (linear ,inaccurate)

Cord A, correct numbers 1 5 11 17 23 31 41 47 59 67 73....

Cord B , correct numbers 3 7 13 19 29 37 43 53 61 71 79....

1	5	11	17	23	31	41	47	59	67	73									
3	7	13	19	29	37	43	53	61	71	79									

$$360/(360/19)=19$$

$$19-16=3$$

See evidence by diagram:

3: Evidence of Dual Prime Number Cord spirals

This is basic mathematics and clearly is that the base is 1:3, the rest of the numbers are fairly obvious. The natural lie of prime number is dual cords of oscillating prime number shown by the two sets of cords(**cord 1,2** and **cord A,B**, further proved by the quadratic algebra and the half- line calculus as shown.). The orientation by symmetry is spiral in a spherical expansion from the -1 zero at the center.

The unravelling of the prime number cords A and B:-1 and -1/3(3 is at the half line and is a unique prime number characteristics

Cord B

$$6/3-7/3 = -1/3$$

$$12/7-13/7 = 1/7$$

$$18/13-19/13=1/13$$

$$28/19-29/19= 1/19$$

$$36/29-37/29=1/29$$

$$42/37-43/37=1/37$$

Cord A

$$4/1-5/1=-1$$

$$10/5-11/5=1/5$$

$$16/11-17/11=1/11$$

$$22/17-23/17=1/17$$

$$30/23-31/23=1/23$$

$$40/31-41/31=1/31$$

Configuration of the basic oscillation of Prime numbers in spiral configuration : which has a built in $\sqrt{360}$ for all numbers periodic Pi value $(360-5/120-7)$ described below for perfect spherical expansion of the Cone as shown further below: The spherical expansion has not been discussed further in the scope of this paper as this is the inherent curvature in the expansion because of the -1 tangent sat the interface of finite and infinite (Sphere collapses into a -1 cone and -1 expands to a sphere) . This mathematics will be published in the future. Basically at $90*4=360nc$, and $120*3=360$ is mathematically curved as at the full cone the value is precisely $\sqrt{360c}$ which for the cone is a curved value, and its squared value is 360 sphere

CORDS,1, 2, prime numbers segregated by the prime number/6=1/6 and prime number/6=5/6 residua, as follows

Cord1 (1/6 residua). 1,7,13,19,31,37,43,61,67, 73,97

Cord 2 (5/6 residua) 5,11,17,23,47,53,59,71,79,83,89

CORDSA,B

Alternate numbers,

1,5,7,11,13,17,19,23,29,31,37,41,43,47,53,59,61,67,71,73,79

CordA : 1,5,11,17,23,31,41,47,59,67,73

CordB :3,7,13,19,29,37,43,53,61,71,79

(1:3)(5:7) (11:13) (17:19) (23:29).....

The synthesis of the 4 cords A,B,1,2 has perfect symmetry as shown below(possibly a spiral progression).

C . arrangement of the oscillation at the half line:The arrangement by spiral oscillation in the inverse cone is further arranged precisely in the configuration of prime number 5 (0,3,5) as per diagram, Pythagoras 1:3 , Pythagoras 1:2 throughout the cone in the matrix itself as shown in diagram 2 This arrangement is in two planes of cord 1,2 and cord A and Cord B as above within the spatial numbered parameter as follows (all prime numbers are placed in the tangent between prime 3 and prime 5 , **Prime 3 and 5 are unique as the base one time expression of a prime number.** *No prime number but 5 ends with 5, and no prime number but 3 has its half $(3/2)=(5*3)/(5*2)$. Prime $3 * 2 = 6$ divisible by 3, but no other primenumber ending with the number 3 (23,43,73,103) when multiplied by 2 can ever be divisible by 3, that's a basic mathematics fact for al prime numbers thus the base prime numbers ending in the digits 1, 3, 5, 7, 9 are exclusivly, 1, 3, 5,7, 19(Exclusive historic fact not understood by current numbers theorists!!), the reverse sequence of this is 18,16,14,12, plus 20,22,24,26. This is mathematical harmony at the base that sets the oscillation of prime numbers. The value 6 is cardinal to the numbers matrix as shown*

(3:5) (3:2)

(6:10)(6:4)

(9:15)(9,6)

(12:20)(12,8)----Prime number 5 configuration. $4*3=12$, $4*2=8$

(15:25)(15,10)--- Prime number 5 configuration, $5*3=15$; $5*2=10$

Results of the synthesis of the two columns at the common half line for spiral oscillation:

General placement of the numbers ,All segregated Prime numbers are lined up by the + 3 column in red . All numbers in column 1 proximate to the half- line marked yellow, have a $residua/6=1/6$. All numbers in green at the half line, but two space away from half line, marked green have a $/6 residua=5/6$. The following placement has been altered for space

1,2

1,2,3,4,5 (3:2)

1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10 (6:4)

1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15(9:6)-

1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20(12:8)

1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25(15:12)

1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30(18:12)

1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,34,
35

24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,34,35,36,37,38,39,40(24:16)

27,28,29,30,31,32,33,34,35,36,37,38,39,40,41,42,43,44,45(27:18)

30,31,32,33,34,35,36,37,38,39,40,41,42,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50(30:20)

33,34,35,36,37,38,39,40,41,42,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50,51,52,53,54,55(33,22)

36,37,38,39,40,41,42,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50,51,52,53,54,55,56,57,58,59,60(36:24)

39,40,41

42,43,44

45,46,47

48,49,50

51,52,53

54,55,56

57,58,59

60,61,63

63,64,65

66,67,68

69,70,71

72,73,74

75,76,77

78,79,78

81,82,83

84,85,86

87,88,89

90,91,92

93,94,95

96,97,98

99,100,101

102,103,104
105,106,107
108,109,111
111,112,113
114,115,116
117,118,119
120,121,123
123,124,125
126,127,128
129,130,131
132,133,134
135,136,137
138,139,140
141,142,143
144,145,146
147,148,149
150,151,152
153,154,155
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159,160,161
162,163,164
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168,169,170
171,172,173
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195,196,197
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243,244,245
246,247,248
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252,253,254
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258,259,260
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264,265,266
267,268,269

270,271,272
273,274,275
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294, 295,296
297,298, 299
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315,316,317
318,319,320
321,322,323
324,325,326
327,328,329
330,331,332
333,334,335
336,337,338
339,340,341
342,343,344
345,346,347
348,349,351
351,352,353

354,355,356

357,358,359

360,361,362

363,364,365

366,367,368

369, 370,371

372,373,374

375,376,377

378,379,380

Results: The Synthesis of the two Cords at the half line showing absolute symmetry and periodic predictable polarity flips at multiples of 6.

C1A C2B

-1 1

3 5

7 11

13 17

19 23

31 29

37 41

43 47

(53 59) -6

(6761) - 6

73 71

79 83

97 89

103 101

109	107	
127	113	
(137	131)	-6
139	149	
(151	157)
163	167	
(173	179)	-6
181	191	
193	197	
(199	211)	-12
223	227	
229	233	
241	239	
(251	257)	-6
(263	269)	-6
(271	277)	-6
283	281	
307	293	
313	311	
331	317	
337	347	
349	353	
367	359	

373	379	
(383	389)	-6
397	401	
9409	419)	-6
421	431	
(433	439)	-6
(443	449)	-6
457	461	
463	467	
487	479	
499	491	
(509	503)	
523	521	
(547	541)	-6
(563	557)	-6
571	569	
577	587	
(599	593)	
(607	601)	
613	617	
(619	631)	-12

- There is a clear demonstrated symmetry of Prime numbers placed in two columns placed at the half line, as above. The half line is at +3 ,shown in red . As a rule all the flips are predictable and are at 6 or multiples of 6

The first such flip of polarity comes at prime numbers 53 and 59 (gap=6)

$$59/6=9.8333333333$$

$$53/6=8.8333333333$$

The next flip is at 67 and 61

$$67/6=11.1666666666$$

$$61/6=10.1666666666$$

The next flip is at

131 and 137

$$131/6=21.8333333333$$

$$137/6=22.8333333333$$

Composite linear at the half line for matrix numbers from above

3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,34,35,36,37,38,39,40,41,42,43,44,45,46,47,48,49,50,51,52,53,54,55,56,57,58,59,60,61,62,63,64,65,66,67,68,69,70,71.

The inverse cone discovered by Vinoo Cameron since 2009 and assented by others 1, translates to a perfect finite Sphere(@-1 center of the sphere), a very difficult understanding for current mathematics, mathematically the value $\sqrt{360}$ at the cone is curved as stated before. This is confirmed by the replication of the Pi value at the cone, shown below, this Pi value replication is constant throughout the entire expanding cone. Note that the center point of the sphere is -1 as shown above, since by simple mathematical logic null zero there cannot be any expansion of the sphere by numbers.

-1

1

5, 4,3,4,5

10,9,8,7,6,7,8,9,10

15,14,13,12,11,10,9,10,11,12,13,14,15

20,19,18,17,16,15,14,13,12,13,14,15,16,17,18,19,20

25,24,23,22,21,20,19,18,17,16,15,16,17,18,19,20,22,23,24,24,25

30,29,28,27,26,25,24,23,22,21,20,19,18,19,20,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30

35,34,33,32,31,30,29,28,27,26,25,24,23,22,21,22,23,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,34,35

40,39,38,37,36,35,34,33,32,31,30,29,28,27,26,25,24,25,26,27,28,29,30,31,32,33,34,35,36,37,38,39,40

The prime numbers at the half line **oscillate as symmetrical arrangement as shown** in the paper, that oscillation of placement indicates a dynamic expansible sphere, not static as per current theory . That symmetry will be infinite as the sphere enlarges, as we plan to show this same at much higher prime number placement values by a novel computer program in dual columns in our research. The **prime number 19 makes 1 composite finite sphere**, by the inverse cone angle of $360/19^\circ$, at Pythagoras 1:3 which is the basis for this number placement ,that is beyond this present basic paper. $\sqrt{(360)-19}=-1/\sqrt{360+19}$. **19 is indeed a representation of 1**. For a sphere to be dynamic, the fixed prime numbers must oscillate in placement, that is a mathematical logic.

Incidental notes on the Pi value as related to Prime numbers: reference to published paper.

$$3 + \frac{1}{7 + \frac{1}{16}} \text{ precise} = 3.14159292035$$

Subsequently it was found that this value equals precisely by digits at the cone first at prime number 5 and 7 as shown and then the same art the cone at Pythagoras 1:3 and further replicated in all periodic values of the cone

$$\frac{360 - 5}{120 - 7} = 3.14159292035,$$

$$\frac{3 - 5}{1 - 7} = -\frac{1}{3}$$

Note that the value+3 and the pi digits by all three methods. The Pi ratio is confirmed as derived from the cone by a simple cross calculus, it is the same value by other two methods.This Pi digit numbers value and +3 by inverse is periodic at the cone and results in a spherical expansion . This is too extensive to discuss in this paper, but it is clear to the authors that the 1:3 cone is inverse of a perfect sphere with -1 at its center ant the sqrt360 value at the cone is curved.

This mathematical proof at three separate locations calls into serious doubt the value of the current Pi accepted by mathematicians as transcendental.We disagree , but the Pi value is incidental to our current focus on the mathematical cone.

NOTES AND CAVEATS

These are secret notes of the lead author Vinoa Cameron, rather etchings to further back the numbers placement at the inverse cone. They demonstrate a fixed tight-1 cone of numbers.

Minus 1 Zero at -1 Coordinate

The base spiral(oscillation at the half-line) of the prime numbers, without a break in continuum is 1 and 3. One leads to the negative spirals, the other to the positive spiral (1:5 and 3:7) representing each cord and un- spiraling this same base spiral by -1 mathematics, we get

Cord B

$$6/3-7/3 = -1/3$$

$$12/7-13/7 = 1/7$$

$$18/13-19/13=1/13$$

$$28/19-29/19= 1/19$$

$$36/29-37/29=1/29$$

$$42/37-43/37=1/37$$

Cord A

$$4/1-5/1=-1$$

$$10/5-11/5=1/5$$

$$16/11-17/11=1/11$$

$$22/17-23/17=1/17$$

$$30/23-31/23=1/23$$

$$40/31-41/31=1/31$$

Caveat 1: This paper delineates the newly discovered created fixed order of Mathematics based on the precise deflection of the inverse cone between infinity and the finite as created at 1:3 Pythagoras and 1:19, this is half the cone , the half-line is in the center at the value 3 and $3 \times (3,6,9,12\dots)$

The spatial configuration and placement of prime numbers at -1 at the cone, is a very difficult understanding, obtained through inspiration. It can be understood by diagrams as the cone represents a perfect sphere. The prime number sieve at 6 is difficult. The most difficult is the placement calculus of the bound spaces configured by prime numbers as shown The sieve is based on placement at number 6 as is shown, it has been manually demonstrated till 50, 0000 prime numbers

Please note above that we have also completely demonstrated by the new Quadratic algebra the prediction of prime numbers in each cord by a calculus of numbers by the new quadratic algebra in section 1(The author at this stage has kept the quadratic algebra secret as this comes under major proofs). This section 11 deals with the placement of the fixed prime numbers at Pythagoras 1:3, the fixed inverse cone at the angle of Genesis (Pythagoras(1:3) . The two cords of the prime numbers are placed at precise fixed points, the base is linear at the center of the matrix of the cone.. Note that prime numbers cords can also be sieved by our sieve at /6 and of course confirmed by the Predictive quadratic algebra(not shown here).

□ The fixed angles in the cone that create the tangent values at the cone for prime numbers are based on the base configuration template of the prime numbers 5 (with number 6) which as the base template is the only prime number of all prime numbers with whole numbers that define Pythagoras 1:3 and Pythagoras 1:2 with matching angles at Pythagoras 1:3 and Pythagoras 1:2 at this template. The rest of the prime numbers are fixed and place at the angle of genesis ($360/19$) , at their half values at a half line of the full cone as explained below, and referenced in the diagram. **Please follow the following caveats precisely to understand prime number placement at the cone**

Caveat 2

As noted on the diagram the basic configuration of the cone is mathematically as follows : that the closure of the cone space at the base of Pythagoras 1:3 with the tangent at Pythagoras 1:2 (see diagram) perfectly defines the template space by the relationship of the two slopes with a common base by a precise factor of $\sqrt{2}$, and that in this unique fixed space also shows that the angle thus subtended at the two Pythagoras ,also absolutely precisely divide to $\sqrt{2}$.

Caveat 3:

The mathematical configuration aligning prime number placement at the cone and angle of genesis is presented in separate steps but the basic configuration is the -1 at the inverse cone(see diagram 3). Prime number 5 and the number 6 by its unique whole number configuration of Pythagoras 1:3 and Pythagoras 1:2, and the precise match of the angles $angle A / angle B = \sqrt{(2)}$ and the hypotenuse for the Pyth1:3,Pyth ($\sqrt{(10)}/\sqrt{(5)} = \sqrt{2}$).

As in the diagram 0...5...6. in the configuration of prime number 5 the upright is 1, and the gap between 5-6 (1). The upright 1 at Pythagoras 1:2 =1 at the Pythagoras 1:3 at 6 the upright is also 1. $5/6+1/6=1$; See diagram 3 .

Also to align the Prime numbers placement in the cone to the inverse cone at the angle of genesis, a unique matching prime number sieve at 6 had been discovered at Hope research for this cone, 6 years ago. It is based on Prime number/6=residua 1/6 and Prime number/6=residua 5/6. It is under research development by a novel dual cord program, the first ever when done by the two authors in our team

Caveat:4

There are two clear proofs that the configuration of 5 and 6 is the basic configuration of prime number placement at the base half line in red and its sagittal divergence in blue , all prime numbers are created in the tangent between blue(5) and red (3) tangent that can be seen in the diagram and also as follows

R B

3:5

6:10

9:15

12:20

15:25

18:30

21:35

24:40

27:45

30:50

33:55

36:60

39:65

42:70

45:75

48:80

51:85

54:90

57:95

60:100

Symmetrical Oscillation of prime number @ 1 , 5 (1/6,5/6)

The following simple trivial arithmetic of placement by 5,6 , note the progression, Cord A numbers in Red , cord B numbers is blue.These are clearly arranged in order.These prime numbers have been sieved by columns in our separate program that is verified. The cords a , b , represents 1/6 , 5/6 residua. The important fact is that these prime numbers are sieved by our placement sieve, as two columns (1/6r,5/6r), that places these oscillations along the whole half-line .This is the oscillation at the half line, a natural proof of the paper. Note the consistent polarity at 6 or multiples of 6

@6*1

$6+1=7$ a

$6+5=11$ b

@6*2=12

$12+1=13$ a

$12+5=17$ b

@6*3=18

$18+1=19$ a

$$18+5=23 \text{ b}$$

$$\textcircled{6*4=24}$$

$$24+1=25$$

$$24+5=29 \text{ a}$$

$$\textcircled{6*5=30}$$

$$30+1=31 \text{ b}$$

$$30+5=35$$

$$\textcircled{6*6=36}$$

$$36+1 = 37 \text{ a}$$

$$36+5=41 \text{ b}$$

$$\textcircled{6*7=42}$$

$$42+1=43 \text{ a}$$

$$42+5=47 \text{ b}$$

$$\textcircled{6*8}$$

$$48+1=49$$

$$48+5=53 \text{ b.....flip(6)}$$

$$\textcircled{6*9=54}$$

$$54+1=55$$

$$54+5=59 \text{ b.....flip(6)}$$

$$\textcircled{6*10=60}$$

$$60+1=61 \text{ a}$$

$$60+5=65$$

@6*11

$66+1=67$ a.....flip(6)

$66+5=71$

@6*12=72

$72+1=73$ a.....flip(6)

$72+5=77$

@6*13=78

$78+1=79$ a.....flip(6)

$78+5=83$ b

@6*14=84

$84+1=85$

$84+5=89$ b

@6*15=90

$90+1=91$

$90+5=95$

@6*16=96

$96+1=97$ a

$96+5=101$ b

@6*17=102

$102+1 =103$ a

$102+5 =107$ b

@6*18=108

$108+1=109$ a

$108+5=113$ b

@6*19=114

$114+1=115$

$114+5=119$

@6*20=120

$120+1=121$

$120+5=125$

@6*21=126

$126+1 =127$ a

$126+5 =131$ b

@6*22=132

$132+1=133$

$132+5=137$ b..... flip(6)

CAVEAT, 5 (See diagram, configuration at prime 5, 1 upright is common to both)

Value 6 @ $360/19^\circ$ (Pythagoras) 1:3 at base 3, 4,5,6) $1^2+3^2=\sqrt{10}$

Value 5 @ $26.79562539225392240^\circ$ (Pythagoras 1:2 at base ,3,4,5) $1^2+2^2 =\sqrt{5}$

At indivisible prime number 5 (3+2), at the point of the cone (perpendicular precisely at 1), by basic Pythagoras equation

$1^2+2^2=\sqrt{(5)}$

$1^2+3^2=\sqrt{(10)}$

$$\sqrt{(10)/\sqrt{(5)}} = \sqrt{(2)}$$

(26.79562539225392240°(Pyth.1:2) / 18.94736842105° (Pyth1:3) = $\sqrt{(2)}$ in degrees proportion.

The angle at Pythagoras is proved correct also separately and current mathematics is at grave error because of the null zero, rather than the correct zero at -1 as shown

Thus this is a perfect fixed trigonometric space, fixed by prime number proportions, and the linear non divergent base is indivisible space ,with the relative prime number values , starting at prime number 5 configuration that

Value 6 @ 360/19°(Pythagoras 1:3) at base3, 4,5,6) $1^2+3^2=\sqrt{10}$

Value 5 @ 26.79562539225392240°(Pythagoras) 1:2 at base ,3,4,5) $1^2+2^2 =\sqrt{5}$

At indivisible prime number 5 (3+2), at the point of the cone (perpendicular precisely at 1), by basic Pythagoras equation $X^2+Y^2=\sqrt{(X^2+Y^2)}$

$$1^2+2^2=\sqrt{(5)}$$

$$1^2+3^2=\sqrt{(10)}$$

$$\sqrt{(10)/\sqrt{(5)}} = \sqrt{(2)}$$

(26.79562539225392240°(Pyth.1:2) / 18.94736842105° (Pyth1:3) = $\sqrt{(2)}$ in degrees proportion.

The angle at Pythagoras is proved correct also separately and current mathematics is at grave error because of the null zero , rather than the correct zero at -1 as shown

Thus this is a perfect fixed trigonometric space, fixed by prime number proportions, and the linear non divergent base is indivisible space , with the relative prime number values , starting at prime number 5 configuration that defines the entire numbers placement at the inverse cone defines the whole cone, below are some of the parameters of this tight cone space that ultimately defines a perfect sphere, and the sphere collapses to this cone space representing -1 by the signature equation and its spiral expansion(reverse spiral when the sphere collapses)

Caveat 7.Numbers constriction :

Numbers are a tight precise fit at the cone(Trigonometric constriction at -1 and numbers constriction of -1 by numbers , match exactly the frame of the cone). All numbers have a constant relationship to the frame of Pythagoras 1:3 cone centered by the value constant19.48683298048. these following are three mathematical parameters.

Reference diagram 1,2 but note the constriction – value K constant

Based on the numbers at 1:3 Pythagoras the negative constriction at half point is as follows. The rest of the values follow. Note the variation from the value at the diagram.

(a).

$$\sqrt{t(10)/3}=1.0540925533$$

At 3:

$$(1.5/1.0540925533)*2-3=-0.1539510561(\text{note the diagrammatic value at 3 versus mathematical value});$$

$$3/0.1539510561=19.4868329805$$

At 7:

$$(3.5/1.0540925533)*2-7=-0.3521691308;7/0,3521691308=19.4868329805$$

At 13

$$(6.5/1.0540925533)*2-13=-0.6671171243;13/0.6671171243=19.4868329805$$

At 19:

$$(9.5/1.0540925533)*2-19=0.97501733551 ; 19/0.97501733551=19.4868329805$$

At 41:

$$(20.5/1.0540925533)*2-41=2.10398477663...41/2.10398477663=19.4868329805$$

Note the precision in trigonometry and numbers, that the -1 constriction is exactly at 19.48683298048. Topology is not constant nor accurate by diagram. The following constant is for all numbers, but at 19 ,it is -1.

At 19

$$a. 19/0.975010561=19.48683298048$$

$$b. (19.48683298048/2) / 1.0540925533 * 2 - 19.48683298048 = -1$$

$$c. \sqrt{19^2 + (19/3)^2} = 20.0277585144 \dots 20.0277585144 / 19.48683295747 = 1.0277585144 \dots 20.0277585144 - 1.0277585144 = 19$$

Caveat 8: -1 at 19 periodic shift by the hypotenuse/slope at Pythagoras 1:3, the constant for all numbers as shown by example .This is +1 periodic shift at 1+18 values, at 19 the switch is to 1 . The periodic shift oscillates between value 18 ,19

At number 1

$$\sqrt{1^2 + 1/3^2} = 1.0509255339$$

$$1.0509255339 / 19.4868329805 = 0.0509255339$$

At number 3

$$\sqrt{1^2 + 3^2} = 3.16227766017$$

$$3.16227766017 / 19.4868329805 = 0.16227766017$$

At number 7

$$\sqrt{7^2 + 7/3^2} = 7.3786478737$$

$$7.3786478937 / 19.4868329805 = 0.3786478737$$

At number 14

$$\sqrt{14^2 + 14/3^2} = 14.75729574745$$

$$14.75729574745 / 19.4868329805 = 0.75729574745$$

At number 19(1+18) (the periodic shift to +1)

$$\sqrt{19^2 + 19/3^2} = 20.02775851561$$

$$20.027758511561 / 19.48683295747 = 1.02775851561$$

At number 36

$$\sqrt{36^2 + (36/3)^2} = 37.94733192202$$

$$37.94733192202 / 19.4868329574 = 1.94733192202$$

At number 37(19+18) periodic shift is to +2

$$\sqrt{37^2 + 37/3^2} = 39.00142447541$$

$$39.001423447541 / 19.4868329808 = 2.00142447782$$

At number 55

$$\sqrt{55^2 + (55/3)^2} = 57.9750909093995$$

$$57.9750909093995 / 19.4868329574 = 2.9750909093995$$

At number 56(37+19), periodic shift to +3

Caveat 9: Quadratic Algebraic calculus for cord prime number prediction by sets:

The calculus for the rational value of X, Y in the quadratic calculus below is very complex, it is not shown here but the quadratic calculus is shown here, it is algebraic. This is new and very difficult, and new and novel and not understandable by current mathematics as is the signature equation.

The easiest way to predict the prime numbers cords is the sieve then by linear program in in single file by the most accurate sieve (Den otter sieve) based on division of numbers by 6, and then segregating every other sieve., This calculus is predictive solution by number set by number and by continuum, so

that there is no error. It is concordant of the calculus by angles that confirms the two cords by the topology of Pythagoras 1:3 very specifically as shown in the diagram. Thus this calculus can only be solved by sets unless the sets are solved by a calculus in continuum of a linear form which cannot replicate the matrix of the spiral form since the two cords are not inter related mathematically and are separated by the twin prime factor of 2 at the base (1,3) and the -1 factor of -1 and -3 as per the unravelling of the two cords.

The settings or Ligand(binding/connecting) relationship by quadratic coordinates for the quadratic calculus for separate prime number sets of Cord A and Cord B (Quadratic Algebra)

The values of the cord can be easily extrapolated by our Prime number sieve at 6 as alternate values starting at prime number 1 (1,3,5,7,11).all the gaps can be extrapolated . The following is the sample proof of prediction from one number to next prime number, sieving the prime sets

The evidence of the two cords is extensive, and written all over the wall of mathematics. The base twin prime is evidence of the dual nature. We have elected not to reference all the evidence in our research that points to dual cords but the ancillary evidence provided here should be more than convincing.

The Prime numbers are by creation placed in sets of three as shown under. The first two numbers as a rule are known from the previous calculus. The calculus is a Quadratic calculus, based on 1:3 check as shown under , that check is a rule for all set. The following Cord A and Cord B sets are demonstrated here for prediction etc. by calculus here

Riemann linear Prime number: 1 3 5 7 11 13 17 19 23 29 31 37 41 43 47 53 59 61

Spiral Cord A numbers : 1 5 11 17 23 31 41 47 59 67 73 83.....

Spiral cord B numbers: 3 7 13 19 29 37 43 53 61 71 79 89...

Cord A sets Cord B sets(These are natural sets)

1 5 (11)	3 7 (13)
5 11 (17)	7 13 (19)
11 17 (23)	13 19 (29)
17 23 (31)19 29 (37)	
23 31 (41)	29 37 (43)
31 41 (47)	37 43 (53)
41 47 (59)	43 53 (61)
47 59 (67)	53 61 (71)

The method and settings of the calculus example of Cord A and B spiral sets:

The numbers calculus must match the geometry. This cone has a linear base at the center and then sloping variable hypotenuse all starting from a point. At the half line prime numbers are placed, in two spiral cords numbers, alternate with each other at the linear base thus binding the matrix. The prime numbers placements oscillate

The coordinates of the settings for Cord A and B examples. The leading edge is always a tangent because one cord numbers are ahead of the others, one advancing and one receding from the point of infinity at the center of the cone

Here is the hint for solution of X and Y in the quadratic coordinates,
 Every cage has a 1:3 ligand This solution here would be muddled, but rational values of X and Y are calculated in this quadratic algebra which is mind boggling and needs a separate paper but here is demonstrated the quadratic algebra for the two cords, may the elite of mathematics not attack us as this is not our cobble stone (Method developed by Vinoo Cameron with assistance of Professor Manoj Srivastava one of the researchers).

Set 61,71,(79)

Cage

$$51 + 30 = 81$$

$$X + Y = 81$$

$$71 + 10 = 81$$

63...X

18...Y

.....
 set 17,23,(31)

Cage

$$11 + 18 = 29$$

$$X + Y = 29$$

$$23 + 6 = 29$$

15...X

14...y

.....
 Stability (all equations of this algebra has the same binding ligand of the equations)

equation 1. $(51 * 3) - 71 = (71 + 51) - (30 + 10) \dots \dots \dots (63 - 30 = 33) (51 - 18 = 33)$

equation 2. $(11 * 3) - 23 = (23 + 11) - (18 + 6) \dots \dots \dots (18 - 15 = 3) (14 - 11 = 3)$

X and Y rotate by polarity placement from set to set , just as prime numbers oscillate

Solution for equations below, Confidential from all

$$[(11 * 3) - 15 = 18] + [(18 * 3) - 14 = 40 \dots 40 + 18 = 58 (29 * 2) \dots \dots 15, 14 \text{ is specific to the cage}]$$

$$[(51 * 3) - 63 = 90] + [(30 * 3) - 18 = 72 \dots \dots 90 + 72 = 162 (81 * 2) \dots \dots 63, 18 \text{ ,is specific to the age}]$$

Set 17, 23, (31) to predict 31, **asan example**

The first two numbers of the prime number tri-set are always known from solving the last set, we know the preceding gap. The set value is as follows for all sets

$$17 \ 23 \ (31) , \text{ set value for the quadratic cage is } 23 + (23-17)=39$$

Quadratic set for this set, unknown except for set value, and 17

$$8 + 15 = 23$$

$$9 + 14 = 23$$

.....

$$17 + 29 = 46$$

Quadratic settings are shown for the sets below

Now the calculus output setting for above set is (Just one value is needed to unravel the other 3 in the quadratic cage, in this case it is 14 (There are many other calculus's but I need just one), which solves the next 31 the predicted number $31-17$ the first number of the set=14. The number 11 is the carry over value from the previous set at position b as a rule throughout

How to convert the prime number to the next prime number in Chain A and B? Precise examples of the quadratic calculus of fixed prime numbers Prediction in overlapping tri-sets as these numbers are at three points of an overlapping triangle / spirals. The sets demonstrated are as follows from Chain A. Unknown next predictive prime number is shown by (n). Note this calculus is also a prime number sieve.

CORD A, PRIME NUMBER SETS CALCULUS:

1, 5, 11 , 17 , 23 , 31, 41 , 47, 59, 67, 73 ,83, 97, 103' 109

Sets:

17 ,23, (31)

23 ,31, (41)

31, 41, (47)

41, 47, (59)

47, 59, (67)

59, 67, (73)

67, 73, (83)

73, 83, (97)

.....

Special note about Quadratic Algebra, a new Algebra.

Warning to readers re the calculus's: This mathematics is alien , so be patient . The following is explanation of the algebra by example of just one calculus and long equation .

The long form equation for the quadratic solution to the coordinates is as under , but short form equation for the quadratic algebra here is an option . This is formal general demonstration of the solution by quadratic algebra: there is always a carry over from the previous equation in all cases

Set 23 31 (41): Example.

15 is the carry over from the quadratic cage of previous set.

31 is the middle number of the set , (41) is the predicted unknown of the tri set

Set value =31+(31-23)=39

Quadratic algebra coordinates, (n)= unknown value to be calculated

15 + 24 =39

(21x) + (18y) =39

31 + 8 =39 (31 is the second number of set , that is so for all sets)

Ligand (binding) values at 1:3 are 24/8=3 ; 24-8=16 ,24+8=32

RULE : The- gaps between the top and the bottom row must be the same total gap with the values of X and Y In this case 16(24-8) and add on 32(24+8) ,in the main Calculation of the middle line values of X, Y: The calculus to place the values of X, Y, is very complex, but follows a set pattern

driven by the 1:3 Ligand (binding) value. 31-21=10 and18-8=10. Also 21-15=6 ;24-18=6

The values must be placed in correct order in the quadratic cage to be rationally bound by 1:3 match for the result for X and Y

Set ,1 5 (11), CORD A

Value-3 carried from base

Set coordinate = 5+(5-1)=9

-3 +12 =9

-1(x)+10(y)=9

5 + 4 =9

Ligand at 1:3=12/4=3 ; 12-4 =8 , 12+4=16. 10 and -1 satisfies that condition as a the sum total of the gap 8 = 2(12-10) +6(10-4); and the gap 5-3=2 equals 5-1=4, -3-1=-2, 4-2=1

Quadratic cage:

6 + -1 =5

-5 + 10=5

.....

$$1 + 9 = 10$$

Next prime number at the set 1, 5 (11) is $1+10=11$

Carry over is -1

.....

Set 5 11 (17), Cord A

Value -1 carry over from previous set

Set coordinate value= $11+(11-5)=17$

$$-1 + 18 = 17$$

$$5X + 12y = 17$$

$11 + 6 = 17$ (11 is the middle number of the set)

Ligand value $18/6=3$ $18+6=24$ $18-6=12$. The rational value of X and Y as per the rules $5=x$ and $12=y$

Quadratic cage:

$$6 + 5 = 11$$

$$-1 + 12 = 11$$

.....

$$5 + 17 = 22$$

So the next unknown number is $5+12 = 17$

Carry over value is 5

Set 11 17 (23) (cord A)

Value 5 carried from the previous quadratic

Set Coordinate : $17+(17-11)=23$

$$5+18 = 23$$

$$X(11) + Y(12) = 23$$

$17 + 6 = 23$ The ligand at 1:3 is $18/6=3$

The rational value, thus based on the resolution by example in the beginning of this algebra section is $X=11, Y=12$

The quadratic cage

$$6 + 11 = 17$$

$$5 + 12 = 17$$

.....

$$11 + 23 = 34$$

Thus $11+12=23$, 23 is the next predicted number in this case equal to set coordinate.

Carry over is 11.

Set 17 23 (31) (cord A)

Value 11 , is carried on from the previous set 11, 17 (23) , not shown here

$$\text{Set coordinate : } 23+(23-17)=29$$

The following are from known values

$$11+18=29$$

$$(15x+14y)=29$$

$$23 + 6=29 \text{ So by rational equation X is 15 , Y is 14}$$

Matching Ligand for $1/3$ is $18/6=3$, above. $18-6=12$, $18+6=24$

The unknown quadratic cage for the set:

$$8 + 15 = 23$$

+ +

$$9 + 14 = 23$$

.....

17 29 46 , known coordinates ($29=23+(23-17$, previous gap))

14 solves the quadratic settings by the span

$$17+14=31$$

$$23-8+15$$

$$23+8=31$$

Carry over value=15

Next set 23 31 (41) (cord A)

Carried over value 15

The following from known values,

$$15 + 24 = 39$$

$$21X + 18Y = 39$$

$31 + 8 = 39$, so by rational mathematics X is 21 Y is 18 at the quadratic below

Matching ligand for 1:3 = $24/8 = 3$, above

$$24 + 15 = 39$$

$$18x + 21y = 39$$

$$31 + 8 = 39 \quad 24/8 = 3$$

Quadratic Cage for this set,

$$10 + 21 = 31$$

$$13 + 18 = 31$$

.....

$$23 + 39 = 62 \dots 31 + (31 - 23) = 39 \text{ known values}$$

18 Solve the quadratic spans follows

$$23 + 18 = 41 \text{ the next number}$$

$$31 - 10 = 21$$

$$31 + 10 = 41$$

$$18 + 31 = 31$$

For the next set the new value **21** is carried over for the next solution

Next set 31 41 (47) (cord A)

Carry over from previous set = 21

$$\text{Set value} = 51 \quad (41 + (41 - 31)) = 51$$

$$21 + 30 = 51$$

$$(35)x + (16)y = 51$$

$41 + 10 = 51$ So X is 35 Y is 16 at the quadratic cage below

Matching ligand for 1:3, $30/10 = 3$; $30 - 10 = 20$; $30 + 10 = 40$

Quadratic Cage, unknown, solved by 35 and 16

$$\text{Set value} = 41 + (41 - 31) = 51$$

$6 + 35 = 41$ (41 is the middle number in this set)

$$25 + 16 = 41$$

.....
 $31 \quad 51 \quad 82$

16 Solve the quadratic span by value 16 solved above,

$$31+16=47$$

$$41-6=35$$

$$41+6=47$$

35 is carried forward.

.....
Next Set 41 47 (59)(cord A)

Carried forward 35

47 is the middle number from set

The following from known values,

$$\text{Set value} = 53(47+(47-41))$$

$$35 + 18 = 53$$

$$(35)y + 18(y)=53$$

$$47 + 6 = 53 \text{ So by rational mathematics } X=35, Y \text{ is } 18$$

Ligand match of 1:3 = 18/6 above; 18-6=12; 18+6=24 . note in this case the gap at the top is zero for valid reasons. (see method above under the start of this section)

Quadratic Cage for the set

$$\text{Set value} = 47+(47-41)=53$$

$$12 + 35 = 47$$

$$29 + 18 = 47$$

.....
 $41 \quad 53 = 94 \dots 47+(47-41)=39$

Solve the quadratic span by value 18, derived above.

$$23+18=41 \text{ the next number}$$

$$31-10=21$$

$$31+10=41$$

$$18+31=31$$

For the next set the new value 35 is carried over for the next solution

.....
Next set 47 59 (67) (cord A)

Carry over= 35,

Set value = 71, $59+(59-47)$

$$35 + 36 = 71$$

$$(51)x + (20)y = 71$$

$59 + 12 = 71$ the rational value of X and Y is thus 20 and 51

Ligand 1:3 match, $36/12=3$; $36-12=24$; $36+12=48$

Quadratic cage for the set:

Set value $71 = 59+(59-47)$

$8 + 51 = 59$ (59 is the middle number in the set)

$$39 + 20 = 59$$

.....
 $47 + 71 = 118$

20 solves the quadratic cage for the next number

$$47+20=67$$

$$59+8=67$$

$$59-8=51-$$

Carry over to next set **51**

.....
Next set is 59 67 (73) (cord A)

Carry over is 51,

Set value = 75 ($67+67-59$)

$$51 + 24 = 75$$

$$(61)x + (14)y = 75$$

$67 + 8 = 75$, so the rational value of X, Y is $61+14=75$

Ligand for $1/3=24/8=3$; $24-8=16$; $24+8=32$

Quadratic Cage for the set

Set value $59 + (67+67-59)=75$

$6 + 61 = 67$ (67 is the middle number of the set)

$$53 + 14 = 67$$

.....

$$59 \quad 75 \quad 134$$

14 value derived above thus solves the next number

Carry over **61**

Next Set 67 73 (83) (cord A)

Carry over 61 and 14 from previous

$$\text{Set value} = 79(73+(73-67))$$

$$61 + 18 = 79$$

$$(63)x + (16)y = 79$$

$$73 + 6 = 79 \text{ so the rational value of X, Y is } 63 + 16 = 79$$

Ligand value for $1/3 = 18/6 = 3$; $18-6=12$; $18+6=24$

Quadratic cage for the set

$$10 + 63 = 73 \text{ (73 is the middle number in the set)}$$

$$57 + 16 = 73$$

.....

$$67 + 79 = 146$$

16 solves the quadratic cage.

Value carried forward **63**

.....

Next set 73 83 (97) (cord A)

$$\text{Set value} = 83 + (83-73) = 93$$

Middle number of set, 83

Carry Over 63

$$\text{Set value} = 83 + (83-73) = 93$$

$$63 + 30 = 93$$

$$(69)x + (24)y = 93$$

$$83 + 10 = 93 \text{ so the rational value of X and Y , 24 , 69}$$

Ligand $1/3$ match for the equation $= 30/10$ above; $30-10=3$; $30+10=40$

Quadratic cage for the set, unknown values:

Set value $93=83+(83-73)$

$$14 \quad 69 \quad =83 \text{ (83 is the middle number in set)}$$

$$59 \quad 24 \quad =83$$

$$73 + \quad 93 \quad =166$$

24 solves the next prime number ,

$$73+24=97$$

$$83+14=97$$

$$59+43=73$$

CORD B PRIME NUMBERS CALCULUS:

3, 7, 13, 19, 29, 37, 43, 53, 61, 71, 79, 89, 101, 107, 113

Sets: (n) means unknown next prime number

$$3, 7, (13)$$

$$7, 13, (19)$$

$$13, 19, (29)$$

$$19, 29, (37)$$

$$29, 37, (43)$$

$$37, 43, (53)$$

$$43, 53, (61)$$

$$53, 61, (71)$$

$$61, 71, (79)$$

$$71, 79, (89)$$

$$79, 89, (101)$$

$$89, 101, (107)$$

.....

Set 3 7 13

Carry forward -1

$$\text{Set coordinate value} = 7 + (7 - 3) = 11$$

$$-1 + 12 = 11$$

$$1x + 10y = 11$$

$$7 + 4 = 11$$

$$1:3 \text{ ligand } 12/4=3 \quad 12-4=8 \quad 3+12=16$$

Quadratic cage

$$6 + 1 = 7$$

$$-3 + 10 = 7$$

$$3 + 11 = 14$$

Next prime number is $3+10=13$

Carry forward **-1**

.....

Set 7 13 (19)

Set coordinate value= $13+(13-7)=19$

Carry over 1

$$1 + 18 = 19$$

$$7x + 12y = 19$$

$13 + 6 = 19$ (13 is the middle number in set)

Ligand @ $1:3=18/6$; $18-6=12$ $18+6=24$

$$6 + 7 = 13$$

$$1 + 12 = 13$$

$$7 + 19 = 26$$

Next unknown prime number $7+12=19$

Carry over **7**

Next set 13, 19, (29)

Carry over 7

Set Coordinate value= $19+(19-13)=25$

$$7 + 18 = 25$$

$$16X + 9Y = 25$$

$$19 + 6 = 25$$

Ligand is $18/6$; $18-6=12$

Quadratic

$$10 + 9 = 19$$

$$3 + 16 = 19$$

$$13 + 25 = 38$$

Next number is $13 + 16 = 29$

Carry over is **9**

Next set 19 29 (37) (cord B)

Carry over 9 from previous set quadratic cage

$$\text{Set value} = 39 \quad (29 + (29 - 19) = 39)$$

$$9 + 30 = 39$$

$$21(x) + 18(y) = 39$$

$$29 + 10 = 39 \text{ so rational value for } X, Y = 21, 18$$

The match for 1:3 ligand is, $30/10 = 3$ above; $30 - 10 = 20$; $30 + 10 = 40$

Unknown quadratic cage for the set:

$$\text{Set value} = 29 + (29 - 19) = 39$$

$$8 + 21 = 29 \text{ (29 is the middle number in the set)}$$

$$11 + 18 = 29$$

.....

$$19 + 39 = 58 \quad 39 = 29 + (29 - 19)$$

18 value solves the quadratic cage and next number (37)

$$19 + 18 = 37$$

$$29 + 8 = 37$$

$$29 - 8 = 21$$

Carry over value = **21**

.....

Next set 29 37 (43)

Value carried over = 21

middle number = 37

$$\text{Set value} = 45 \quad (37 + (37 - 29))$$

$$21 + 24 = 45$$

$$(31)x + (14)y = 45$$

37 + 8 = 45 so the rational value of X and Y is 31+14= 45

Ligand proof of 1:3 = 24/8=3 above ;24-8=16;24+8=32

Quadratic Cage for the set:

$$6 + 31=37 \text{ (37 is the middle number in the set)}$$

$$23 + 14=37$$

.....

$$29 + 16 = 45 \text{ } 45=37+(37-29)$$

14 solves the next quadratic cage

$$29+14=43$$

$$37+6=43$$

$$31+ 6=37$$

Carry over to next set is 31

.....

Next set 37 43 (53) (cord B)

Carry over from previous set=31

$$\text{Set value} = 49 \text{ (43+(43-37)}$$

$$31 + 18 = 49$$

$$(33)x + (16)y = 49$$

43 + 6 = 49 so the rational value for X and Y is 16 , 33

Ligand match for 1/3=18/6=3, 18-6=12;18+6=24

Quadratic cage for the set

$$\text{Set value}= 43+(43-37)= 49$$

$$10 + 33 =43 \text{ (43 is the middle number of set)}$$

$$27 + 16 =43$$

.....

$$37 + 16 = 53$$

16 solves the quadratic values and the next prime number,

$$37+16=53$$

$$43+10=53$$

Carry over to next set 33

.....

Next set 43 53 61 (cord B)

Carry over from previous set 33

$$\text{Set value} = 63 (53+(53-43))$$

$$33 + 30 = 63$$

$$(45)x + (18)y = 63$$

$$53 + 10 = 63, \text{ so the rational value for X, Y, } 18+45=63$$

Ligand match at 1:3 is 30/10

Quadratic cage for the set

$$\text{Set value } 63=53+(53-43)$$

$$8 + 45 = 53$$

$$35 + 18 = 53$$

.....

$$43 + 63 = 106$$

18 solves the quadratic for the next prime number ,

$$43+18=61$$

$$53+8=61$$

Value carried over=45

.....

53 61 (71)

Carry over value =45

$$\text{Set value:} = 69 (61 +(61-53))$$

$$45 + 24 = 69$$

$$(51)x + (18)y = 69$$

$$61 + 8 = 69 : \text{ the rational value of X and Y} = 18 + 51 = 69$$

Ligand at 1:3 = 24/8 ;24-8=16 ;24+8=32.

Quadratic cage for the set:

$$10 + 51 = 61$$

$$43 + 18 = 61$$

.....

$$53 + 69 = 122$$

18 solves the next prime number,

$$53 + 18 = 71$$

$$61 + 8 = 69$$

Value carried over = 51

.....

Next set 61 71 (79)

Carry over value = 51

$$\text{Set value} = 81(71 + (71 - 61))$$

$$51 + 30 = 81$$

$$63X + 18y = 81$$

$$71 + 10 = 81 \text{ rational value for X and Y ; } 18 + 63 = 81$$

$$\text{Ligand 1:3 for this } = 30/10 = 3; 30 - 10 = 20; 30 + 10 = 40$$

Quadratic Cage for this set:

$$\text{Set value} = 81(71 + (71 - 61))$$

$$8 + 63 = 71$$

$$53 + 18 = 71$$

.....

$$61 + 71 = 142$$

18 solves for the next prime number at the quadratic cage.

$$61 + 18 = 79 \text{ next number}$$

$$71 + 8 = 79$$

Carryover = 63

Next set 71 79 (89)

Carryover value = 63

$$\text{Set value} = 87(79 + (79 - 71))$$

$$63 + 24 = 87$$

$$(69)x + (18)x = 87$$

79 + 8 = 87 this solved rationally by X=69 Y =18

Ligand value at 1:3 = 24/8=3; 24-8=16; 24+8=32

Quadratic Cage:

$$10 + 69 = 79$$

$$61 + 18 = 79$$

18 solves the next number

$$71 + 18 = 89$$

$$79 + 10 = 89$$

Carry over to next set 69

Next set 79 89 (101)

Carry over 69

Set value = 99 (89 + (89 - 79))

$$69 + 30 = 99$$

$$(77)x + (22)y = 99$$

89 + 10 = 99 the rational value for X and Y = 77, 22

Ligand at 1:3 = 30/10 ; 30-10=20; 30+10=40

Quadratic cage:

$$12 + 77 = 89$$

$$67 + 22 = 89$$

$$79 + 99 = 178$$

22 solves the cage and the next prime number.

$$79 + 22 = 101$$

$$89 + 12 = 101$$

The carry over number is 77.....

The 6Pi and 8 Pi configuration:

$$(6 * 3.14159292035) - (6.3.1622776601) = 0.1241084385$$

$$6 * 3.14159292035 = 18.8495575221$$

$$6 * 3.16227766017 = 18.97366596102$$

$$0.97366596102-0.124108438=0.84955752302$$

$$0.84955752302/0.14159292035=6 \text{ precise}$$

At 8

$$(8*3.14159292035)-(8*3.1622776601)=0.165477918$$

$$8*3.14159292935=25.1327433628$$

$$8*3.16227766017=25.29822128136$$

$$0.29822128136-0.165477918=0.132374336336$$

$$0.132374336336/0.1415929203=0.9375$$

That is why there is oscillation by prime numbers because not all numbers are affected by the curvature functional curvatures of the cone expansion to form a sphere, that's why there is symmetry.

This is absolute proof of the inverse is evident in the paper as proved by me on Pi digits and Pythagoras 1:3. The constant is $(360-5)/(120-7)$; $3+1/(7+1/16)$ OR $3+0.14159292035$ Precise. For every +3 there is prime number placement as shown at the half line. Plus the constant for every +3 the constant ratio of expansion is $3+1/(7+1/16)$ OR $3+0.14159292035$, This is great and final proof against this mathematics which is practiced at your journal and all others, a wrong mathematics. Brother I walk away from all this , this is all yours to see through at your journal , no matter , a book will be produced under your name and my name only.

The sphere cannot expand but at 3+as *proved to you by the Exact PI digits at all +3 expansion. What else prove is there about -1 inverse cone, you who knows topology!!!. The square expands at +4 (1,4,8,12,16,20,24,28,32,36,40,44,48) Einstein's use of 8 Pi to define the curvature is nonsense, I said that, so I and you are not part of current mathematics*

$$\begin{array}{r}
 + \\
 30 \\
 27 \\
 24 \\
 21 \\
 18 \\
 15 \\
 12 \\
 9 \\
 6 \\
 3 \\
 - \\
 +30 \ 27 \ 24 \ 21 \ 18 \ 15 \ 12 \ 9 \ 6 \ 3 \ - \ 1 \ - \ 3 \ 6 \ 9 \ 12 \ 15 \ 18 \ 21 \ 24 \ 27 \ 30+
 \end{array}$$

-
3
6
9
12
15
18
21
24
27
30

1.Prime numbers are placed at two separate cords and two separate columns, one cord ascending from base 1, the other descending to base 3. The two cord columns, one hugging the half line at 3, the other column being a space away.The Synthesis of the two columns and the two cords summarize the oscillation between the two cords showing absolute symmetry and periodic predictable polarity flips at multiples of 6. This suggests a spiral arrangements of expanding prime numbers by their oscillation at the half lines with very consistent flips at multiple of 6 . All this is predictable in several ways, but primarily the placement sieve of the columns which has been confirmed till 50,000 prime numbers manually, and is scheduled to be developed into long numbers sieve.

2.The precise spherical expansion is presented mathematically as proof of inverse Pi, the sphere emerges at every 6 (6,12,18,24..)value as well as the Flips the circumference becomes a progressive sphere , as

$$6*\sqrt{10}=\sqrt{360}$$

At value 6: $(6\pi)-(6*\sqrt{10})=0.12410843859$ Note $6*\sqrt{10}=\sqrt{360}$ curved value($^2=360$ curved)

$$6\pi = 18.8495575221 - 18 = 0.8495575221$$

$0.8495575221/0.14159292035$ (digits of the Pi)=6 precise

3. All numbers constriction and the -01 constriction at value 19 and subsequent progression at progressive values of 18, 19 , is shown in the text as pure mathematics.

RESULTS:

Basically we have proved the placement and oscillation of Prime numbers and all numbers at the half line in the basic configuration of the -1 cone at Pythagoras 1:3 . It is clear that the half- line is for all times at +3, the cone is defined as a collapse of a sphere and the inverse cone by its curved expansion at the edges (curved $\sqrt{360}$ value). The angle $360/19$ degrees precise proves current trigonometry as in precise and not accurate mathematically. The results will lead to much science and the correction of the mathematics of Isaac Newton and Albert Einstein.

Basically it is proven that dynamic expansion of bound space from the leastparticle , to the maximal finite is modulated with an inverse cone at -1 Vedic zero ; that cone has the same precise configuration in

its least as well as its maximum finite. There is no such thing as null zero , and there is no such thing as current mathematics.

CONCLUSION:

The universe of mathematics by mathematical logic is precisely applicable to all space and speed at the half line in the configuration of the least unit of space to the maximum, the configuration is an expanding inverse cone at -1 that is inverse to a perfect finite sphere i.e. the collapse of a sphere cannot result in “nothing” because the base cone space is the least as created and indestructible. All numbers are arranged and placed by a half- line. The universe of mathematics is finite as described. Prime numbers are a spiral oscillation by cords at the half line of an inverse cone that expands precisely as a sphere, all these placements are predictable including the flips at the spiral and the spherical enlargement. Einstein’s use of 8 PI to calculate the curvature in his use of mathematical tensor was, we believe in error (6pi is the standard at $\sqrt{(360)}$). Additionally application of the -1 mathematics to Einstein’s theory and the work of Isaac Newton will make it clearer and simpler, that work has started at hope research.

DIAGRAMS AND DOCUMENTS:

Diagram #1

LINEAR

COMPOSITE Pythagoras 1:3, Pythagoras 1:2

The exverse is an enlarging sphere.

This is the half line and half cone. All numbers are concentric at -1 center

INVERSE CONE AT -1

$$3 + (3 + 1) = 2^2 \cdot 19$$

$$3 - (3 + 1) = 2^2 \cdot -1$$

Diagram #2

Diagram #3

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